
TEACHERS' CHARACTERISTICS AS DETERMINANTS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS LEARNING OUTCOMES IN ISLAMIC STUDIES IN OYO EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF OYO STATE

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Abstract

This research work was based on teachers' factors as predictors of secondary school students' learning outcomes in Islamic studies in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State. Ten public secondary schools were randomly drawn from the selected schools. The sample comprised Islamic studies teachers. Relevant data in relation to the study were collected from the participating respondents with the aid of questionnaire items that were admitted to fifty (50) respondents. The data collected were analyzed using mean and weighted average to determine students' learning outcomes in Islamic studies in public senior secondary schools, enumerate the teachers factors as predictors of secondary school students' learning outcomes such as competency, attitudes and interest. Recommendations were made to achieve positive learning outcomes and chart prospects for Islamic studies in Oyo East Local Government public secondary schools in order to produce vibrant, religious and articulate Muslim children for the development and growth of the Nation (Nigeria).

Keywords: Teachers' Characteristics, Determinants, Secondary School Students Learning Outcomes and Islamic Studies

Introduction

Formal education is one of the core instruments that enable a nation to develop rapidly. It is indisputable fact that every country of the world has maintained that huge part of the yearly budget must be given to education for a nation to excel socially, politically and economically the various aspects of their education would be evaluated to see and infuse the lacking concepts and processes that will aid national growth and development. Teaching and learning revolve around teachers who are crucial to policy formulation and implementation in education sector. This is because they are the custodians of the whole process; they supervise and implement whatever education policy developed by government, so the role of teachers in the educational sectors cannot be under-estimated.

Learning is basically for students and pupils who wish to learn and explore the hidden phenomena of the world. Teachers have the fundamental roles of making the students to learn through his systemic ways of teaching known as methodology in researching context. In other way, the primary role of teachers is teaching which some scholars of education have defined as "the promotion of learning". Teaching is viewed by Umar (2014) as "the art of impacting knowledge, he knows that to teach the learners and ways of impacting the knowledge in the most effective way possible. This implies that teaching is not just telling the learners stories; it is all about knowing exactly what to give to learners and the best way to make them retain what is impacted to them. Therefore, teachers are very much instrumental in the learning process. In other way progress of any sort made in any given society is largely determined by the quality of the teachers in such society. Furthermore, all prestigious professions and high paid jobs are products of the creativity of teachers. An Arab poet has said in respect of teacher translation "it is on his shoulders others rise to glory, he is nothing but a ladder for climbing the mountain. The poet explains therefore why the role of teacher in a society is basic, crucial and indispensable. In another vein, it is a misconception to accept the public statement that the reward of teachers is in the Heaven. No matter reward gained by the teachers in this world cannot be commensurate with the kind of service rendered by the teacher. Moreover, teachers serve as the connector of the learners with the materials they want to learn from.

In other words, the teacher interacts with the learner and material separately before bringing them together for learning process. Thus, without the teacher, the material will not get to the student and the material will be useless. The definition of a teacher would not be effective without such a teacher having good methodology which is the scientific aspect of teaching and learning the most technical aspect where learner displays a large amount of information on the topic taught in the class. It is clear that the teacher who taught the topic was very effective in his or her teaching (Ekweme, 2001).

Thus, teachers determine the information their learners take in. Sade and Bahli (2013) explained that the functions of teaching which is done by teachers must contribute to the improvement of the learning process because ensuring learning is the sole purpose of teaching. The role played by a teacher is acknowledged in the Nigeria education policy. The stipulated national policy on education affirms that the quality of education system depends on teacher (FRN, 2004). Holistically, teacher determines the present and future of any given society and that is the reason why teachers are to be maintained inwardly and outwardly by a teacher should not be one way or the other be compromised with anything.

Other relevant factors that affect students' performance are teachers and attitude of students. These are considered to be factors that determine students' poor learning outcome in

Islamic studies. Likewise positive attitude, interest, dedication are among the qualities of a competent Islamic studies teachers, that can affect good learning outcomes for Islamic studies students. Hence, this study focuses on teachers' factor as predictor of secondary school students' learning outcome in Islamic studies in selected secondary schools in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Statement of the Problem

Islamic studies being a religious subject is expected to contribute positively to the high quality of education in the country. Moreover, the subject as taught in school is expected to be one of the reformers of the Nigeria society. Being what it is, the effectiveness of this role can only be assessed by the learning outcomes of the students. Considering the teacher factors in the learning process, it is not out of place to say that Islamic studies teachers are among the predictors of the learning outcomes of the Islamic studies students who are used to measure the objectives of subject and the effectiveness of its role in the Nigeria's society. Hence, the teacher factors needs to be studied to be able to unveil the roles of Islamic studies teachers in ensuring learning in Islamic studies classes, this is why this study is necessary.

Research Questions

To achieve the aim of this study which is teachers' factors as predictors of secondary school students' learning outcomes in Islamic studies in Oyo East Local Government, the following questions are posed:

1. What are the effects of Islamic teachers' attitudes on students' learning outcome in Islamic studies?
2. Are there relationships between educational qualifications of teachers of Islamic Studies and students' learning outcomes?
3. Of what relevance is the teachers' experience to students' academic performance?

Scope of the Study

This study is targeted at Islamic studies teachers' factor as predictors of students' learning outcome in Islamic studies. This study is limited to the teachers' academic qualification and general attitudes. The study also covered ten (10) public junior secondary schools, five Islamic studies teachers in ten (10) selected schools in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study guide governments at all levels of administration on teachers' factors to be considered to ensure desirable learning outcome in students. It also serves as a measure for school administrators in their activities. Moreover, it exposes Islamic studies teachers to some potential factors they need to deplore in order to achieve the aims and objectives of teaching-learning of Islamic studies. It also guide the policy makers, curriculum planners, book writers and community at large in considering teacher factors in their policy, books and curriculum respectively.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The Concept of Teacher

Generally, a teacher is a person who has been professionally trained to engage in the art of imparting knowledge on the learners. A teacher knows what to teach the learners and the ways to teach them; a teacher helps learners to learn. He guides learners to behave in certain manners beneficial to themselves and the society at large (Umar, 2004).

Teachers are one of the most important elements of the school. A teacher is an expert career possessor who undertakes the government's education, instructional and related administrative duties (Erden, 2007). Teachers are the most important element in terms of reaching the school aims. Hence, teachers are the secret heroes of school management. The success of an educational system cannot be considered separate from the success of the teachers who put into action and carry out the dictates of the system; they undertake the duty to educate young generations who will bring the countries into the future influential world (Hotman, 2000).

Teacher as a concept has been defined by several scholars and at different for their reasons. Robinson (2008) says "the teacher initiates a set of activities in which his pupils take part so that the result is the acquisition of a set of skills that will become permanent in the pupils by means of regular practice." Also, the National Policy on Education (2004) stipulates that on completion of training the student-teacher is expected to be loyal citizen of the state, person of high moral standard and integrity, knowledgeable, progressive and effective teacher who can inspire pupils and challenge them to learn.

Ismail (2003) says a teacher is a person who imparts knowledge, wisdom and information on a pupil so as to bring permanent change in behaviour. This implies that a teacher is a person who brings about changes in the behaviour of others from negative to positive. Adebayo (1998) explains that the teacher as a person engaged in the teaching profession from the pre-primary to tertiary institution; this means that a teacher is a person trained to help in learning in classroom situation in order to achieve a set of educational goals. Muhammad (1998) says that teachers in the world over are known to engage in character molding, intellectual development and nation building. Hence, teachers are the producers of the experts in all works of human life; engineers, doctors, pharmacists, armed forces personnel, administrators, politicians, scientists, educationists, among others.

Students' Learning Outcome

Learning outcomes according to Mrunal and Manvinder (2017), are written statements of what the successful student/ learner is expected to be able to achieve at the end of the programme module/ course unit or qualification. The evidence of learning does not only mean through grades from the traditional assessment practices, it is an expected and increasing demand by various educational stakeholders who want documentation that demonstrates the entire process of learning for accountability (Chambers and Wickersham, 2008). The teachers play a significant role in the intellectual development of their students, using various assessment techniques and teaching styles to improve their performance in school subject, this helps in measuring students' progress. Melissa (2009) views academic performance to mean how students deal with their studies and how they can cope with or accomplish different tasks given to them by their teacher. This means academic performance is the ability to study and remember facts and be able to communicate effectively. Teachers are very important and have great influence on students' academic achievement and also play

a critical role in educational pursuance of students (Ayanniyi, 2004). The effective teachers or instructors pride themselves on having positive student interactions in and out of classroom, provide prompt feedback and encourage teamwork among students. Also, the most impactful teachers obtain and implement constructive feedback, and use different techniques to encourage active learning oriented towards students becoming self-directed, independent and critical thinkers (Paolini, 2015).

In educational institutions, success is measured by academic performance or how a student meets standards set out by school or examination bodies. Aubrey (1970) explains performance as activities that goals are consistently being met effective and in efficient manner, performance is the effectiveness and improvement of students toward specific goals set up to be achieved. Parents care for their children's academic performance because they believe that good academic results will provide more career choices, and broader job opportunities. The school is interested in fostering good habit for the same reason, but it is often influenced by concerns about the school's reputation and the possibility of monetary aid from government institution which can hinge on the overall academic performance of the school. States and federal departments of education are charged with improving school standards and making use of relevant methods of measuring success in order to bring about positive improvement in education.

Academic performance in the school is evaluated in a number of ways. For regular grading, students demonstrate their knowledge after undergoing written and oral tests, performing persecutions, and participating in class activities (Thomas, 2007). Teachers evaluate in form of letter or number grades and side notes to describe how well students understand. Guben (1984) finds that one way of finding out how teachers have taught over a period of time is to examine whether instruction has been teacher-centered or student-centered or a mixture of the two in varying degrees. Teacher-centred instruction means that a teacher controls what is taught when and under whatever condition within his or her classroom.

The influence of teachers' teaching effectiveness on the learning outcome of students as measured by students' academic performance has been the subject of several studies; effective teaching is a significant predictor of students' academic achievement (Adediwura, 2007). Therefore, effective teachers are expected to produce students of higher academic performance. Teachers have significant influence on students' academic achievement; however, other factors such as socio-economic background, family support, aptitude, personality of student, self-confidence, interest of student also determine his success in academic performance. On the other hand, teacher's age, qualification, mastery of subject-matter, experience have significant role on students' academic performance.

Finally, poor academic performance of student in Nigeria has been linked to poor teacher's performance in terms of accomplishing the teaching strategies which have attributed to poor motivation. Oredein (2000) observes that conditions that make for effective teaching to take place are availability of the resources to the teachers and, general condition of infrastructure. Absence of these needed conditions will definitely bring about a negative result in public schools, which may translate to poor academic performance, attitude and values.

The Concept of Islamic Studies

Islamic Studies is a multi-Disciplinary and inter-disciplinary subject taught in all the major universities across the globe. At the post primary institutions, it is called Islamic Religious Studies (I.R.S). The Subject comprises of the study of the Qur'an, Hadith, Fiqh, spirituality, Islamic civilization, human rights, ethics, gender studies e.t.c Islamic Studies field according

to Azniwiti, Mohamed, Mohammad and Azlina (2016), requires Arabic language as a medium since it is a discipline of al-Naqli knowledge which is based on the knowledge in Arabic language where all the basic sources of Islamic studies namely al-Qur'an, Haith and Thurath books are in Arabic language Education in Islam is the most important needed requirement after proclamation of faith; it is so because one cannot properly worship or understand Allah without it. Education is one of the pillars that support Islamic faith. Scholars at different times have explained the concept of Islamic education in different ways. For instance, Khusro (1979) sees Islamic education as that thing which aims at a balanced growth of the total personality of human through the training of man's spirit. Islamic (Studies) education is viewed as the process of awakening the learner's consciousness of the Creator as the foundation of knowledge of the world around, and to inculcate a sense of responsibility to the Creator El-Yakub (2007). It is geared toward having the correct knowledge of how to worship Allah and to train the mind and personality of the learners toward the best moral and social conduct as well as to become a law-abiding member of the society.

Islamic education preaches humanitarianism, universal love, universal benevolence, and it aims at universal fraternity and repels all forms of racialism and sectarianism, so far as human rights and privileges are concerned (Farid, 2009). It makes no distinction between prince and peasant, Lord and Vassal, rich and poor. It is also preaches peace, love and equality of men. Islam is a total and unconditional submission to the will of Allah. It is a religion of peace, security, freedom and salvation. It is a religion that encourages education and science and also enjoins purification and cleanliness.

To this end, the concept of Islamic studies is very relevant to all Muslims since its aim is to inculcate in the learners the fear of the Lord, which will generate a morally sound society. This knowledge guides the teacher easily towards achieving concepts. If the students are taught very well by qualified, quality and competent teachers who have the mastery of the subject-matter, such teaching will, no doubt, influence the performance of students academically especially in their Junior Secondary School Examination.

Islamic education refers to the process involving three references: the individual, the society or nation, community and the whole content of reality both material and spiritual, which play a dominant role in determining the nature and destiny of man and the society. Thus, Islamic education can be said to be the social, economic and political behaviour of mankind as the best means of creating a new generation of young men and women who will not lose touch with their own tradition and will not at the same time become intellectually retarded or educationally backward or unaware of development in any branch of human knowledge.

Yunus (2000) observes that Islamic education is aimed at training Muslim youths in the correct method of adjusting themselves to a changing environment. It is through such goal that the system of Islamic education cannot be found as luxurious as the western type of education, the aim of Islamic education is to instill moral in the minds of students. According to Hussein (1979), Islamic education is an education which trains the sensibility of pupils in such a manner that their attitude to life as well as their actions, decision and approaches to all kinds of knowledge are geared toward all round success.

Objectives of Islamic Education in Secondary School

The aims and objectives of Islamic Studies have been projected by both WAEC and UTME examination syllabi as making students to acquire knowledge in Islamic Studies with regards to the following:

- (i) The historical and contemporary development of Islam as well as lessons learnt from them;
- (ii) The spiritual, moral, socio-economic and intellectual roles of Islam in society and
- (iii) The practical application of Islamic teachings in daily life (www.myschoolgist.com.ng)

The aims of the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME-Islamic Studies) include the following:

- (i) To master the Qur'an and sunnah as foundations of Islamic and social life
- (ii) To be familiar with the Islamic heritage, culture and civilization
- (iii) To be acquainted with the tradition of Islamic scholarship and intellectual discourse
- (iv) To demonstrate knowledge of Islamic moral, spiritual, political and social values and
- (v) To be prepared to face the challenges of life as good practicing Muslims

The importance of knowledge can never be overemphasized in Islam. Allah the Exalted used His knowledge to create Adam and his wife, Eve, and also created and provided all what they needed to survive. Adam and Eve was the first spouse created by Allah. Allah out of His bounties endowed Adam with knowledge which made him superior to all Angels (Qur'an 2:31 - 32). Jah (1982) explains that to understand the objectives of Islamic education, one must first understand the philosophy of Islam itself. Islam is not a religion which confines its activities to promoting spiritual welfare of man rather it is a complete way of life which encompasses all aspects of life. Its educational philosophy in the view of Al-Ghazali ventilated by Muhammad (2019), should be derived from the Qur'an and thus must reflect character formation, brightening the heart, moral and societal development.

Islam teaches the life in this world as a beginning to an external life in the hereafter. As it is clear, education is a dynamic side of philosophy. Education without philosophy is blind and philosophy without education is unacceptable. Islamic education aims at building a foundation of faith in Allah and submission to His Will, achieving balanced humanity, inspiring unity and sound brotherhood, attaining knowledge for the recognition of everyone's right, obedience and respect of law, getting trained to become emotionally and mentally stable (<https://www.guidance.edu.bd>). Muhammad (2009) submits that it aims at the balanced growth of the total balanced personality of human acronym as it infuses into the whole of one's personality and create an emotional nafs al- mutmainnah attached to Islam and enables one to follow the Qur'an and the sunnah of the Prophet.

1. Believing in Allah and His Prophet Muhammad; this is the fundamental principle on which Islam is based. The believers are aware of the divine laws which govern the universe and human beings;
2. Knowledge of Allah and seeking self-perfection;
3. Discharging his duties and making judgements on the basis of knowledge (man's role should be to establish orderliness, human brotherhood, freedom, equality and social justice);
4. Being capable of observing, analyzing, synthesizing critical judgements being guided in all these by the inner light of Islamic faith;

5. Being capable of self-teaching and perfection in the moral and intellectual fields.

Hence, the aims and objectives of Islamic education are basically to develop the personality of the individual who should be religious, moral, honest, sociable, humble, generous, kind, patient, obedient, tolerant and lenient to all mankind regardless of their social status, tribe, race, rank and nationality. Thus, the purpose of Islamic education is to give meaning to life and enrich it with the light of Islamic faith as outlined in the Qur'an in order to strengthen and advance human societies.

Qualities of a Good Islamic Studies Teacher

Abdullah and Jasim (2014) are of the view that good education having teachers of good qualities is the most essential in the making of educational and civilized society and in providing human capital. They also observe and submit that our national education system needs to be upgraded by strategic, dynamic and comprehensive efforts to upgrade the abilities and skills to the highest quality and excellence. Producing excellent and quality teachers of Islamic education besides enhancing the teaching profession according to Rahala (2011), require education, mentoring, tutoring and guidance from the Islamic education lecturers especially excellent Islamic education lecturers with great quality of character. It needs be mentioned too that the quality of a great personality is pertinent and this according to B. Salwana (2009) includes being visionary, responsible, confident, innovative, caring, lovely, empathetic, supportive, competent as a problem solver, fair, efficient, flexible, committed to the task, creative, cooperative, hardworking, open and sharp-minded, integrity-measured, friendly and appreciating others, To know the qualities of a good teacher is very important because it helps teachers to understand their position. Hamid (1989) cited in Haruna (2012) itemizes the following as the qualities of an Islamic studies teacher:

1. He should have true academic and intellectual capacity; that is, he should have a good grounding in the science of Islam, and be well read in general culture of Islam.
2. He should have wealth of knowledge of the subject matter especially in Arabic and vast knowledge of the Qur'an and Hadith because they are the sources of Islamic studies, Moreover, all their contents are in Arabic. Translated books are not enough for teaching Islamic studies owing to the fact that no two language that are the same.
3. He should have the moral ability to be able to educate his students in such a way that they will become fully aware of the perfect according between their teacher's word and his actual behaviour. Teacher of other subject too must be men and women with moral belief for their functions are to impart what they teach in religiously healthy way which promotes growth of knowledge and to develop the mind. The teacher's moral attitude has undoubtedly a far reaching effect upon the minds of his young pupils. The relationship which is established between teachers and students throughout the year, and thereafter, must have a lasting impression. An Islamic studies teacher is expected to be knowledgeable in Qur'an, Hadith and Arabic, and should be up to date in his subject area, not pretending to know it all; he should be willing to learn from students.

Islamic teachers care for a child as if it is his own child, connects children with knowledge, counts his/her reward with Allah, motivates children to think and be active and must be a role model for his students (<https://islamisawayoflifeawayofteaching.wordpress.com/2018/05/05/5-qualities-of-a-muslim-teacher/>). Azram (2018) observes that teaching profession is noble and given high status in the society because the nature of the job is next to that of parents and thus, a teacher should be able to discover those vast reserves inside the students, inspire and

encourage them to strive for greatness. Self- concept of individuals correlates with the culture and the work practices and it affects their work behaviours (Mohd, 2013) while Elhoshi, Ebong Bioumy, Abdullah and Nawi (2017) , conclude that when one has a close relationship with God, one's attitude and behaviours would tend to be consistent with the rules and stipulations of the religion.

Teachers' Academic Qualification as Predictor of Students' Learning Outcome

Teachers' qualification goes a long way to effect student's performance in academics. The teacher's assignments according to Enwelm (2016), depend on their qualifications on the subjects being taught as there exists the tendency that teachers holding higher qualifications like Bachelors and Masters degrees in subject they teach perform better and be more productive. Sumayya (2018) complements Enwelm's view when he submits that teacher with good certification and licensing status tend to influence students' learning through stability and confidence in the class. Interest in students' performance and teachers' qualification has intensified among education policy makers and researchers. Definitely, what the teacher does in the view of Akiri (2013), influences the whole process of learning and effective teacher produces better performing students while Koedel (2007) and Maphoso and Mahlo (2015), admit that qualification or the quality of the teachers employed to teach students are crucial and obviously advantageous. To understand how many students are taught by the teacher lacking specified levels of training, efforts have been focused on the mismatches between teachers' qualification and their teaching assignment (National Commission on Teacher Qualification, 1996).

One of the main findings concerning teachers' qualification has been the relatively high incidence of teachers teaching subjects outside their areas of specialization, training and certification. Area of specialization speaks volume in the mastery of subject matter. According to Kamamia, Ngugi and Ihinguri (2014), the mastery of subject matter is an essential skill that a teacher requires to be endowed with to know what they are teaching simply because it implies that the teacher is able to grasp the main points and teach them to the learners. When the teacher specializes on the subject to be taught, it equips the teacher with the scholarly knowledge of the subject and integrates with the professional education leading to new understandings and skills for professional performance (Shantz and Latham, 2012) Olowoyeye and Alonge (2014) submit that there is a high correlation between what teachers know and what they teach because the ability to teach effectively depends on the teacher's knowledge of the subject matter.

National Policy on Education in FRN (2014), on teacher's qualification, specifies that the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) shall be the minimum teaching qualification. Others include B.Ed, B.Sc. (Ed), PGDE, B.A (Ed), M.Ed., Ph.D. and other relevant teaching qualifications. The Colleges of Education have positively responded to this policy provision by reviewing their curriculum to meet the challenges posed by this policy (FRN, 2014). Qualification equips the teacher, and provides the enabling environment needed for a child to attain his or her full potential. However, Blossom, Gibbona and David (2007) observed that an impact on standard achievement is clearly the most important criteria for evaluating teacher's quality. According to Morgan (2005) and Hayes (2000), the qualification of a teacher is a crucial factor in promoting effective learning in schools.

They adds that teacher's quality should include mastery of subject matter, and good teachers do not pretend to know it all, but are willing to learn from pupils, monitor and evaluate children's progress, show personal qualities composure, show flexibility in responding to

pupils needs, develop critical thinking abilities and so on. It is important to recognize that qualification and mastery of subject-matter are the major factors in performance of students, and will not be comprehended effective without good teaching. Mastery of subject-matter is one of the most important issues in the quality of teaching profession; we may be able to say that the mastering of subject matter is a crucial factor promoting effective learning in school. Effective teaching requires individuals who are academically able and care about the well-being of children and youth.

Suleiman (2001) says mastery of subject matter is a key to gaining sound and effective knowledge, and that a teacher is the one who is highly knowledgeable and up to date in his subject area and is willing to impart his knowledge. Yunus (2009) explicates that there is no gain saying that mastering of subject matter is important in teaching-learning process. This is because no teacher teaches what he knows not. And a half-baked teacher is as devastating to the society as anything. A teacher in the traditional classroom is seen as an embodiment of knowledge, an epitome of wisdom who is expected to impart knowledge on students. Presently, the emphasis has shifted to ensuring that students become active participation in the teaching-learning process, to which the teacher is just a facilitator. Teachers' mastering of subject-matter cannot be relegated; a teacher who does not master his subject-matter cannot facilitate learning for students. Instead of leading the students to new discoveries, he will rather be an epidemic to the society. Mastering of subject-matter by a teacher is the backbone of both teaching and learning process.

2.3 Appraisal of Literature Review

There have been different studies related to teachers being predictors of students' learning outcome. A study conducted by David (2016) to investigate the teacher and teaching effects on students' academic performance, attitudes and behaviours admits that teachers have substantial impacts on their students' academic and life-long success. With the research among a subset of teachers who were randomly assigned to class rosters within schools., he establishes that there exists a wide range relationship between the productive validity of teacher effect estimates on students' attitudes and behaviours qualification on students' performance revealed that teachers' qualifications have strong effects on students' performance. He sampled twenty government owned junior secondary schools within Kaduna State and concluded that the schools lacked competent teachers and the students' performance was poor as a result of incompetent teachers. He then recommended that the teachers should be encouraged to acquire higher qualification.

Ugbe and Agim (2009) carried out research investigating the influence of teachers' competence on students' academic performance in Senior Secondary school Chemistry and found out that Chemistry students taught by qualified and experienced teachers performed significantly better than those taught by unqualified and inexperienced teachers. The duo used a random sampling technique to select 6 secondary schools out of 12 secondary schools in Yala Local Government Area of Cross River State. 200 students, 20 teachers and 6 principals were used in the study. In carrying out the research, a survey design was adopted. Three researcher-made instruments namely School Principal Questionnaires (SPQ), Teachers Competence Questionnaires (TCQ) and Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) were used to gather data for the study. Ebenezer, Daniel, Sophia, Micah and Margaret (2015), investigated into the relationship between the quality teachers and students' academic performance in Sekondi Takorandi Metropolitan Assembly (STMA) Junior High School teachers and Pupils in the metropolis with the result that the quality of teachers was high in terms of their academic and professional qualifications but that did not reflect much in the performance of

the students. They randomly selected five educational circuits in the metropolis for the conduct of the study where stratified and systematic sampling techniques were used to sample participants and the sample size was 500 while questionnaire was mainly used for the data collection and Pearson Moment Correlation, ANOVA, percentage and Standard deviations were deployed to analyze the data collected.

The teachers' qualifications and experience are important factors contributing to students' performance, but the experience influence performance more than qualifications. Based on the findings, he recommended that government should employ highly qualified and experienced teachers.

Finally, this research is conducted to investigate the teachers' factor in the learning outcome of Islamic studies students in junior secondary school with a view to uncovering the influence and giving useful recommendations for further policy formation that will ensure national growth in our education system.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive design. This design describes, finds out and interprets conditions among various variables of teacher interest, attitude and competency. The objective is to see how teachers' factor can predict the learning outcome of students.

Population of the Study

The target population for the study comprises all Islamic studies teachers in all public secondary schools in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State. Random sampling technique was used to select fifty (50) Islamic studies teachers in the study area. In such school five Islamic studies teachers were randomly selected to administer the prepared questionnaire in the selected ten public secondary schools.

Research Instrument

Questionnaire was used to obtain primary data for this study is self-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire contains four (4) sections. Section "A" is on the demographical information of the respondents, which include name of school, gender, class taught, religion, academic qualification and teaching experience and partly explains how the questionnaire is to be filled, while other sections focus on research questions.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

The instrument was subjected to face and content validity to ensure that it measured what it is expected to measure at the reliability level of 8.5.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher shall administer the questionnaire with the assistance of one research assistance that will assist in the distribution and collection of the questionnaires.

Methods of Data Analysis

Data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, such as frequency count and simple percentage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Academic Qualification of Respondents

Academic Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
NCE	31	62.0
B.Ed	12	24.0
M.Ed	4	8.0
Others	3	6.0
Total	50	100.

Table 4.3 reveals the academic qualification of respondents. 31 (62%) of the respondents are NCE holders, 12 (24%) of them are B.Ed holders, 4 (8%) of them have M.Ed qualification and the remaining 3 (6%) of the respondents have other academic qualifications.

Working experience of respondents, 29 (58%) of the 5 - 10 years of teaching experience, 13 (26%) of the 10 - 15 years of teaching experience. Also, 6 (12%) of the 15 - 20 years of teaching experience while the remaining 2 (4%) of the respondents have more than 20 years of teaching experience?

Table 4.4: Teachers' Attitudes and Students' Learning Outcome in Islamic Studies

S/N	Statements	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagreed (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Means	Rank
1.	Teachers' emotional state affects students learning outcome in Islamic studies.	23 (46.0)	17 (34.0)	7(14.0)	3(6.0)	3.20	2 nd
2.	It is necessary to motivate students in learning Islamic studies.	19 (38.0)	25 (50.0)	5 (10.0)	1 (2.0)	3.24	1 st
3.	Teachers' punctuality affects students' learning outcome in Islamic studies	15 (30.0)	25 (50.0)	2 (4.0)	8 (16.0)	2.94	5 th
4.	Islamic studies teachers are classroom teachers as well as religious leaders.	17 (34.0)	23 (46.0)	4 (8.0)	6 (12.0)	3.02	4 th
5.	Uses of harsh and abusive language affect students' learning outcomes in Islamic studies.	18 (36.0)	22 (44.0)	9 (18.0)	1 (2.0)	3.14	3 rd
6.	Teachers' mode of dressing stimulates students' learning outcome in Islamic studies.	15 (30.0)	14 (28.0)	11 (22.0)	10 (20.0)	2.68	7 th
7.	Allowing students to take active part in learning influences their learning outcome in Islamic studies.	10 (20.0)	17 (34.0)	14 (28.0)	9 (18.0)	2.56	8 th

8.	Giving students constant assignments influence their students' learning outcome in Islamic studies.	11 (22.0)	16 (32.0)	10 (20.0)	13 (26.0)	2.50	9 th
9.	Inferiority complex of Islamic studies teachers affects students' learning outcome.	8 (16.0)	12 (24.0)	17 (34.0)	13 (26.0)	2.30	10 th
10.	Remarkable attitude of the Islamic studies teachers influences students' learning outcome in Islamic studies.	20 (40.0)	9 (18.0)	7 (14.0)	14 (28.0)	2.70	6 th

Source: Author's (Computation 2022)

Table 4.4 above reveals respondents' perception on the effect of teachers' attitude on students' learning outcome. The table reveals that frequency count of responses and percentage weight based on the four-point likert scale. From the table, the mean column reveals mean values for each of the responses to question items under section B of the questionnaire. As revealed in the table, mean value of 3.20 implies that on the average respondents agree that teachers' emotional state affects students learning outcome in Islamic studies. The means value of 3.24 shows that respondents also agreed that it is necessary to motivate students in learning Islamic studies. Mean value of 2.94 reveals that on the average respondents disagreed that teachers' punctuality affects students' learning outcome in Islamic studies.

They however agreed that the Islamic studies teachers are classroom teachers as well as religious leaders as shown by the mean value of 3.02. On the average respondents also agree that uses of harsh and abusive language affect students' learning outcomes in Islamic studies as revealed by the mean value of 3.14. Mean value of 2.68 also revealed teachers' mode of dressing stimulates students' learning outcome in Islamic studies. Also mean value of 2.56 shows that respondents agreed that allowing students to take active part in learning influence their learning outcome in Islamic studies, also mean value of 2.5 shows that on the average respondents agreed that giving students constant assignment influence their students' learning outcome in Islamic studies. Also, from the Table, mean value of 2.3 shoes that respondents disagreed that inferiority complex of Islamic studies teachers can affect students' learning outcome in Islamic studies, while they agreed as revealed by the mea value of 2.70 that remarkable attitude of the Islamic studies teachers influence students' learning outcome in Islamic studies.

Summary of Findings

This research work was carried out in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State. The title of the research was teachers' factors as predictors of secondary school students' learning outcome in Oyo East Local Government Ares of Oyo state. The study covered SS1 and SS2 in which ten schools were selected in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State. The study adopted descriptive survey method.

This study revealed that teachers influence students' learning outcomes in Islamic Studies in the study area. It was found that teachers' attitudinal factors such as ability to motivate students, ability to manage emotion, the use of abusive language and punctuality are the major factors that influence students' learning outcome in Islamic Studies. This study revealed that teachers' competence factors such as adequate knowledge of the use of

appropriate instructional materials, mastery of subject matter, ability to teach from simple to complex, ability to communicate well with students, ability to recognize students' individual differences and ability to adopt appropriate teaching methodology rank as the major competence factors that influence students' learning outcome in Islamic Studies. This study also revealed that incompetence of teachers, poor attitude of students, lack of rapport between the students and teachers, inadequate parental support and inadequate infrastructural facilities are the major factors militating against the teachers' effort towards achieving good learning outcome in Islamic Studies.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that teachers' factor is a significant determinant of students' learning outcome in secondary schools in the study area. It is therefore necessary that Islamic studies teachers motivate students and help them recognize their strengths and weaknesses. Teachers are important role models for students and have a big impact on helping shape, create, support and establish students' strengths, goals and knowledge. It is essential for teachers to be aware of effective qualities, skills and characteristics that they bring into learning environment as this plays a significant role in influencing not only the academic outcome but also the general attitude of students.

Teachers preparation and knowledge of teaching and learning, experience, subject matter knowledge and certificate all establish teacher's effectiveness in class and these by extension influences students' academic performance in the study area. Students' learning can be positively impacted by the encouragement of teachers to their students. A teacher's influence ideas and expectations of his or her students' capabilities have an effect on student academic performance and achievements. When teachers believe in their students, their students begin to believe in themselves. Students take into effect the belief their teachers have on them and accept it as part of who they are and their abilities.

When students are viewed in a negative way by their teacher such as being lazy, unmotivated and having no abilities, they take on those believes about themselves and this translates into differential behaviour towards their students and ultimately affects their academic performance. Therefore, teachers' factors such as attitude, expression, motivation and competence should be adequately considered to achieve excellent learning outcomes in Islamic studies in secondary schools in Oyo East Local Government Area.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that Islamic studies teachers are made aware of the significance of teachers' factors in determining students' learning outcome so as to device necessary means to enhance students' performance. Teachers should be adequately trained and continuously sensitized on the need to adopt teaching best practices that impact on their attitude and competence to aid students' academic performance in Islamic studies. Islamic studies teachers should be friendly to students to ignite their interest in learning and ultimately enhance their performance in Islamic studies.

Parents should be sensitized on the need to support and encourage their children in their quest to learn as this will motivate them to perform well in their studies and strengthen teacher to parent relationship which is germane to achieving good learning outcome among students. Government should also endeavour to provide adequate instructional resources to secondary schools in the study area and as well provide funds needed to put necessary facilities in place, as these will enhance students' learning outcomes.

Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge TETFUND, Nigeria for funding this research.

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